

How To Better Engage with ASIS&T Members? Lessons Learned from SIG-III's Activities during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Potnis, Devendra

Gala, Bhakti

Reyes, Vanessa

Lamba, Manika

Warraich, Nosheen Fatima

Seifi, Leili

Perez, Paul Jason

The University of Tennessee at Knoxville, USA | dpotnis@utk.edu

Central University of Gujarat, India | bhakti.gala@cug.ac.in

University of South Florida, USA | vanessareyes@usf.edu

University of Delhi, India | lambamanika07@gmail.com

University of the Punjab, Pakistan | nosheen.im@pu.edu.pk

University of Birjand, Iran | leili.seifi@birjand.ac.ir

University of the Philippines, Philippines | pj@slis.upd.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

Collaborative engagement with members is crucial to sustained membership in professional associations. It also empowers members to connect, build, and grow relationships across large special interest groups (SIGs) within a widely networked professional association. However, members of professional associations increasingly experience a lack of belonging, social disconnectedness, and disengagement. As of 2022, the ASIS&T SIG-International Information Issues (SIG-III) had over 620 members. One of the challenges of having such a large member base is maintaining engagement and finding ways to connect with an international community of academics and information professionals. Engaging with geographically scattered and culturally diverse members is a demanding situation resulting in weak ties among community members. In this panel presentation, the speakers are officers and members who planned, organized and carried out various successful initiatives. They will share the initiatives they undertook to promote engagement among SIG-III members, the best practices for implementing those initiatives, the lessons learned from their experiences and the results. Other SIGs, Chapters, and professional associations can benefit from the critical lessons shared during this panel.

KEYWORDS

Engagement, Social Connectedness, Collaboration, Professional Network, International Information Issues

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Individuals become members of professional associations for personal benefits such as networking, developing a professional identity, attending conferences and events, accessing resources, and more (Ki Weng, 2016; Hager, 2013; Markova et al., 2013; Stevenson, 2013;). Retaining membership in a professional association is a challenge across professions directly linked to an individual's engagement with the association (Wang & Ki, 2017; Yeager, 1983). Studies on engagement motivation among professional association members have found that personal incentives like professional networking opportunities are insufficient to sustain member interest and engagement (Hager, 2013). The social and professional connections among members serve as the foundation for the growth and development of a professional organization.

The ASIS&T Special Interest Group of International Information (III) issues which celebrated its 40th anniversary in 2022, had over 620 members representing a cross-section of members from across the world. SIG-III represents a significant chunk of ASIS&T's international member base that is geographically scattered and culturally diverse. The COVID-19 pandemic accentuated the social disruption with the lack of physical gatherings.

To better engage and connect this community of ASIS&T members, SIG-III launched various initiatives. Officers and members implemented these initiatives (a) to fulfill the broad missions of the SIG-III to promote awareness among ASIS&T members and information professionals of the importance of international cooperation; (b) to facilitate and enhance better communication and interaction among ASIS&T members and their foreign colleagues on information issues; and (c) to develop a global network of digital scholars developing countries, and to provide a forum for exploring and discussing international information issues and problems. The elected officials strive to design and develop initiatives to fulfill the above-stated objectives. In addition, SIG-III leadership has created several special initiatives so that members who do not hold officers but are interested in serving SIG-III can actively contribute to creating more value for ASIS&T members. These endeavors have fostered interest and growth and encouraged members to take pride in leading and participating in SIG-wide activities such as research collaboration, mentorships, and informal social sessions facilitating communications that otherwise would not be possible during the COVID-19 pandemic.

PANEL ORGANIZATION (75 MINS)

Officers and members of the ASIS&T SIG-III who led popular initiatives for engaging with the community will share their experiences of planning these initiatives, challenges faced, and lessons learned. The panel will answer the following three questions: 1. What was done by SIG-III to better engage with the community members during the COVID-19 pandemic? 2. How was it implemented, and what were the challenges faced? 3. What are the lessons learned from these experiences of engaging with community members? Finally, we will engage with the audience.

What: Engagement with Community (15 MINS)

SIG-III has engaged with its members for several years through International Paper Contest, InfoShare Program, Newsletters, and website and social media platforms.

After taking the reins in 2020, the SIG-III chair conducted an online survey to collect the expectations of all members of the SIG. To meet these expectations, SIG-III leadership launched new initiatives. For instance, SIG-III celebrated the success of its members by seeking their key accomplishments via an online survey and broadcasting the responses of 17 members via SIG-III's social media channels. In addition, the SIG-III Chair and officers gathered interest among members and carried out the following initiatives. To cater to one of the expectations of members, we decided to launch the "Research wing" initiative that would serve as an interface between junior LIS researchers and professionals in developing countries (i.e., mentees) and senior and experienced researchers (i.e., mentors). To make this process inclusive, we conducted two online meetings that over 25 members attended. Their concerns and feedback were recorded and helped us propose the procedure to implement this initiative. SIG-III also conducted two meetings with ASIS&T South Asia and Africa Chapter members. These meetings aimed to learn and discuss the challenges of conducting and publishing research in developing countries. These two meetings, attended by over 30 members of both chapters, led to a panel on "Conducting and publishing research in developing countries: Challenges and solutions" at the 84th Annual Meeting of ASIS&T (Potnis et al., 2021). Panelists included officers and members of SIG-III, ASIS&T Africa Chapter, and ASIS&T South Asia Chapter. This panel acknowledges ideas and concerns shared by all the attendees. SIG-III organized a flipped panel on "[Publishing research in reputed venues](#)." Panelists from Africa, Asia, Europe, and North America were requested to record their guidance in advance. SIG-III chair uploaded these recordings to the ASIS&T iConnect Library two weeks before the panel. During the synchronous panel, members asked questions to the panelists. As a result, SIG-III members have lifetime access to the recordings of the panelists' guidance and the one-hour Q&A session.

SIG-III Chair-Elect and two members from Asia and North America, who did not hold any officer position, launched an initiative to strengthen professional networks and provide a unified experience to members. This task involved planning a series of casual café styled virtual meetings, all themed to create a welcoming and stress-free environment among members. From this partnership, the SIG-III Café International initiative was born. It involved hosting four bi-monthly meetings themed in various leisurely formats, attracting members to freely exchange hobbies and research and fostering new unlikely collaborations among the disciplines. At the end of these sessions, we conducted a series of surveys that led to some key findings about how important it is to have informal events for members to easily carry out conversations while building their network and getting to know their SIG-III community. SIG-III Co-Chair and International Paper Contest Chair moderated two workshops on "Publishing impactful research" and "How to employ theories and analyze data for publishing LIS research." See <https://www.asist.org/2022/08/26/sigiii-workshop-2022-09-21>. Over 200 ASIS&T members registered and attended these workshops live via Zoom. Finally, SIG-III Webmaster/Communication officer uploaded the recordings of these workshops on SIG-III's YouTube channel for all current and future members.

How: Planning, Implementation, and Challenges (20 MINS)

As a facilitator of multiple synchronous meetings with ASIS&T members from different backgrounds, it was difficult for the SIG-III Chair to make these meetings inclusive and not let seniors or a few members dominate the conversation. Monitoring a video conversation and chat simultaneously was also daunting, especially when 30 attendees burst with and challenged each other's ideas on the Zoom call. Sample solutions were as follows: Building an inclusive culture via email communications on iConnect, conducting Doodle polls for scheduling meetings at times that work for most members, setting the rules and norms of communication at the beginning of the Zoom calls, acknowledging and respecting everyone's ideas, encouraging attendees not to commit to a single idea or a solution prematurely, inviting attendees to list their ideas in a live document hosted on a cloud platform, incorporating their feedback, and asking Zoom attendees to switch off their audios when they are not participating in the conversation. For the flipped panel, we ensured to identify panelists who represent different types of diversities, suggested topics that do not overlap, and reminded panelists to submit their recorded guidance two weeks before the panel. Hence, members get plenty of time to watch the recordings and ask relevant questions to the panelists during the panel.

Two members of SIG-III planned and implemented a series of online café meetings around different themes. The café meetings gave SIG members a sense of social connectedness, with themed sessions that provided an informal

platform for members to seek professional guidance from our community members. We noted that social connectedness encourages collegiality (the trust and respect members had for each other enabled negotiation and the ability to work in sub-teams); and fosters a safe and positive environment with a sense of belonging (McClunie-Trust et al., 2022). The elements of social connectedness such as support, trust, kindness, friendships, and collaboration (Potnis et al., 2020; Krämer et al., 2021; Katzy et al., 2011; Levin & Cross, 2004; Constant et al., 1996) were studied in informal virtual environments. As part of this initiative, members had the opportunity to share informal professional and non-professional issues in a safe space. The execution and challenges that were faced during the implementation of the series of café meets will be discussed, including brainstorming sessions, the basic structure of the meets, exploration of different themes for each session, designing of flyers, exploration of different tools for activities, marketing, participation of the members, and the feedback form.

SIG-III Co-Chair and International Paper Contest Chair planned and conducted online research workshops. However, deciding the content and topic for the ASIS&T community, managing the time, and the registration of 200+ participants were the challenges. Both workshops were interactive, full of learning, and received excellent participant feedback. We knew about the topics participants were interested in learning and were willing to have more research workshops to improve their research skills.

SIG-III is one of the largest communities in ASIS&T and informs its members about updates and activities that are difficult due to cross-cultural and cross-time zone communication issues. One main challenge is misunderstandings due to cultural differences in communication styles and norms. For example, some cultures may be more direct in their communication, while others may be more indirect, leading to confusion or offense if not properly understood. Moreover, the time difference between people in various parts of the world can make coordination and real-time communication difficult, leading to delays and potential misunderstandings. Despite these challenges, Webmaster/Communication Officer effectively leveraged social media to spread expert guidance, member achievements, and other support online. SIG-III launched its YouTube channel and used other social media platforms, like Twitter and Facebook, to share news updates with members. In addition, information about the events always included the time zone and details on joining the virtual meeting platform.

So What? Lessons Learnt and Future Direction (10 MINS)

Sample lessons include: 1) periodically reaching out to members to understand their needs and expectations from the SIG; 2) designing initiatives to cater to the member aspirations and needs; 3) periodic meetings of officers to build a community of practice for social bonding, creating a sense of belonging, and sharing experiences, challenges, and solutions; 4) expanding leadership opportunities to non-elected members; 5) creating accountability among officers and members responsible for leading initiatives; 6) SIG leadership regularly guiding officers and answering their queries; creating new initiatives and officer positions for catering to the needs of a growing the SIG; 7) investing in technology for facilitating better collaboration among members (e.g., annual subscription to the Zoom Pro account); 8) harnessing a sense of belonging among members; maintaining a positive and enthusiastic culture via iConnect communication platform; 9) collaborating with other chapters (e.g., meetings with South Asia, Africa chapters) and SIGs; 10) actively using the SIG communication platforms for promoting professional activities to foster professional development; 11) extending opportunities to non-officers to create a sense of belonging; and 12) being communicative and responsive. In the future, we aim to promote awareness of international issues among information professionals in developing countries and network and increase members in developing countries through available platforms.

Engagement with the audience (25 MINS)

After the presentation, the panel members and the moderator will engage with the audience using icebreaker activities and invite them to share their ideas on the following questions: What is engagement within a large international community of scholars/researchers? How can we increase engagement from members? Can the lessons we learned be applied to your scholarly communities? The audience will also get an opportunity to ask questions.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

By the end of the panel discussion, the audience will understand how SIG-III officers engage with the community. It will promote the SIG-III initiatives among the professional community/ASIS&T members. We expect other SIGs, Chapters, and professional associations to benefit from the best practices shared. The critical lessons learned from our experiences and the outcomes can motivate and help implement successful initiatives to promote engagement and sustain memberships among members of professional associations.

PANEL MEMBERS

Devendra Potnis is an associate professor at the University of Tennessee at Knoxville. His research focuses on accessing and using information tools, resources, and services. He has published research in GIQ, IPM, IJIM, IT for Development, Journal of Information Science, JMIR, JASIS&T, LISR, Telematics and Informatics, The Information Society, and other journals. He has published with 74 scholars from 28 countries. He received funding from IMLS,

OCLC, and ALISE. He is the recipient of the "Member of the Year" award for his service to ASIS&T. Under his leadership, SIG-III won the "SIG of the Year" award.

Bhakti Gala is an assistant professor at the Central University of Gujarat, India. Her research interests include information literacy, cultural heritage information, digital libraries, and metadata. She has published in IPM, LISR, Library Quarterly, First Monday, and DESIDOC Bulletin, among others. She led a team of eight researchers from South Asia on the 2022 ASIS&T Chapter Special Project and has worked as a consultant on projects funded by OCLC, ALISE, and the University of Hong Kong. Bhakti received the 2022 James E Cretsos Award for Leadership, the 2022 Chapter Member of the Year Award, and the 2014 SIG-III IPC Best Paper Award.

Vanessa Reyes is an Assistant Professor of Instruction in the School of Information at the University of South Florida. She is the Editor-in-Chief of the Florida Libraries Journal and Director-at-Large for Beta Phi Mu International Honor Society. Her research contributes to the emerging field of personal information management (PIM), quantifying how individual users organize, manage, and preserve digital information. She has published research in PDT&C, SAA, IJIDI, The Information Professional and other journals. Her latest book *Saving Your Digital Past, Present and Future, A Step-by-Step Guide*, is a widely used digital life management resource.

Manika Lamba has recently completed her Ph.D. in Information Science from the University of Delhi, India. Her research focuses on information retrieval, digital libraries, social informatics, and scholarly communication using NLP, and machine learning techniques. In addition to publishing scholarly articles, she has published two books. Currently, she is serving as the Editor-in-Chief of IJLIS, and the Chair of the Professional Development Sub-Committee at the IFLA STL Section. She has received funding from Princeton University, NSF, ASIS&T, and SICSS. ASIS&T SA chapter received the "Best Publication" Award in 2022 for the Newsletter designed and edited by her.

Nosheen Fatima Warraich is a Professor and Director at the Institute of Information Management, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. She is a recipient of the Fulbright post-doc fellowship in 2015 at the State University of New York at Albany, New York, and the ASIS&T New Leader Award in 2017. Her research is published in prestigious journals in the field, including the Journal of Librarianship and Information Science, Electronic Library, Journal of Academic Librarianship, Library Hi Tech, Interactive Learning Environments, and other journals. She is the editor of a Scopus-indexed journal titled "Pakistan Journal of Information Management & Libraries."

Laili Seifi is an Associate Professor at the University of Birjand, Iran. Some of her professional services include being an organizer of international conferences, Chair-Elect of SIG-III 2022-2023, Board of directors & chair of the scientific event of the Association of Iranian Public Libraries, and Chair of Dr. George Atiyeh Prize during 2021 & 2022. Dr. Seifi was awarded the Erasmus Mundus scholarship at the University of Warsaw, Poland, in 2012. Her research interests include the digital preservation of cultural heritage, indigenous knowledge management, public libraries, and information literacy. She has published research in Library management, IFLA, and other journals.

Paul Jason Perez is an Assistant Professor in the School of Library and Information Studies at the University of the Philippines, where he teaches introductory courses on LIS, ICT, and Programming. He finished his Bachelor of LIS from the same school. In 2019, he completed his Master of Digital Information Management from the University of Technology Sydney through the Australia Awards Scholarship. His latest projects and publications can be accessed on his website at <https://www.pjperez.xyz/>.

CONCLUSION

Exemplary leadership demonstrated by the SIG-III officers, member-centric innovative initiatives, leveraging appropriate technology solutions, and inclusiveness, consistency, and agility in implementing these initiatives rejuvenated enthusiasm and social bonding among members. As a result, over 300 members directly engaged with SIG-III activities, and many more benefitted from them. Thirty-five members ran for over 20 officer positions in 2022-23, which also attests to the ability of SIG-III's activities during the COVID-19 pandemic to enhance member interest. SIG-III carefully grooms future leaders to sustain member engagement and popularity among members worldwide.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This panel is sponsored by SIG-III.

REFERENCES

- Constant, D., Sproull, L., & Kiesler, S. (1996). The kindness of strangers: The usefulness of electronic weak ties for technical advice. *Organization Science*, 91(2), 143-150. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3250814>.
- Hager, M. (2013). Engagement motivations in professional associations. *Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly*, 43(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0899764013502582>

- Katzy, B., Stettina, C., Groenewegen, L., & de Groot, M. J. (2011). Managing weak ties in collaborative work. In *17th International Conference on Concurrent Enterprising*, Aachen, Germany, pp. 1-9. <https://www.infona.pl/resource/bwmeta1.element.ieee-art-000006041247>
- Ki, E. & Wang, Y. (2016). Membership benefits matter: Exploring the factors influencing members' behavioral intentions in professional associations. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 27(2), 199-217. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21230>
- Ki, E. & Wang, Y. (2018). Membership matters: Why members engage with professional associations. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 29, 71-82. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11266-017-9873-x>
- Levin, D. Z., & Cross, R. (2004). The Strength of Weak Ties You Can Trust: The mediating role of trust in effective knowledge transfer. *Management Science*, 50(11), 1477–1490. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1030.0136>
- Markova, G., Ford, R., Dickson, D & Bohn, T. (2013). Professional associations and members' benefits: What's in it for me? *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 23(4), 491-510. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.21076>
- Mcclunie-Trust, P., Jones, V., Winnington, R., Shannon, K., Donaldson, A., Macdiarmid, R., Jarden, R., Turner, R., Merrick, E., & Andersen, P. (2022). Doing case study research collaboratively: The benefits for researchers. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1177/16094069221096296>
- Potnis, D., Gala, B., Lwoga, E., Islam, M., Warraich, N., Keah, H., & Rorissa, A. (2021). Conducting and publishing research in developing countries: Challenges and opportunities. *Proceedings of the Association of Information Science and Technology*, 58(1), 634-638. <https://asistdl.onlineibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/pa2.516>
- Potnis, D., Gala, B., & Deosthali, K. (2020). Investigating "message forwarding behavior" of mobile phone users: Exploring the link between message content, user sentiment, and user intention to forward messages on social media-based instant messaging platforms. *First Monday*, 25(8). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v25i8.10651>
- Stevenson, S. (2013). 96 Benefits and Services that Attract, Retain Members. In S. C. Stevenson (Ed.), *Member Benefits* (pp. 4–51). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118704097.ch1>